

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE RESEARCH GUIDE

MISTRAL INNOVATIVE TRAINING NETWORK 2022

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MISTRAL-ITN Social Acceptance Research Protocol

1. Introduction

MISTRAL (**M**ulti-sectoral approaches to **I**nnovative **S**kills **T**raining for **R**enewable energy & **s**oci**A**L acceptance) is training a new generation of researchers who can evaluate the complexity of social acceptance issues facing the deployment of renewable energy infrastructure and the transition to low carbon energy systems, and propose innovative solutions in a variety of research, government, and business contexts. The project began in 2019 and finishes at the end of 2022. The network has beneficiaries in the United Kingdom, Portugal, Denmark, Germany, Switzerland, and Ireland, and a vast range of partner institutions and experts supporting the research carried out in the project ¹. At the heart of the network are 15 Early Stage Researchers, pursuing PhDs in the beneficiary universities and generating new knowledge on current and future challenges on social acceptance of renewable energy and the energy transition.

This report seeks to provide a reflection on the research completed within the network by combining the accumulated knowledge of the MISTRAL network on key social acceptance variables and key papers addressing them, providing a 'travel guide' to social acceptance research for those embarking on research on social dimensions of renewable energy and the energy transition. In the last section of this report, you can also find research conducted by the MISTRAL-ITN Early Stage Researchers. This acts as a guide for a range of key concepts commonly used in research on the special acceptance of renewable energy, although there are a number of existing review papers that reflect on the overall research field, which include:

- Batel, S., (2020), Research on the social acceptance of renewable energy technologies: Past, present and future. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 68, p.101544.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101544>
- Carley, S., Konisky, D. M., Atiq, Z., & Land, N. (2020). Energy infrastructure, NIMBYism, and public opinion: a systematic literature review of three decades of empirical survey literature. *Environmental Research Letters*, 15(9), 093007.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab875d>
- Devine-Wright, P., (2008), Reconsidering public acceptance of renewable energy technologies: a critical review, chapter in Jamasb T., Grubb, M., Pollitt, M. (Eds) *Delivering a low carbon electricity system: technologies, economics and policy*, Cambridge University Press. Online copy [here](#).
- Ellis, G. and Ferraro, G., (2016), *The social acceptance of wind energy*. JRC Science for Policy Report, European Commission, Brussels. Available [here](#)
- Fast, S., (2013), Social acceptance of renewable energy: Trends, concepts, and geographies. *Geography Compass*, 7(12), pp.853-866.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12086>
- Lundheim, S.H., Pellegrini-Masini, G., Klöckner, C.A. and Geiss, S., (2022), Developing a theoretical framework to explain the social acceptability of wind energy. *Energies*, 15(14), p.4934.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/en15144934>

¹ <https://mistral-itn.eu/>

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- Rand, J. and Hoen, B., (2017), Thirty years of North American wind energy acceptance research: What have we learned?. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 29, pp.135-148.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2017.05.019>
- Segreto, M., Principe, L., Desormeaux, A., Torre, M., Tomassetti, L., Tratzi, P., Paolini, V. and Petracchini, F., (2020), Trends in social acceptance of renewable energy across Europe—A literature review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(24), p.9161. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17249161>

2. Core Definitions

This first section reviews a number of core concepts in social acceptance research and highlights a range of literature that offer key guidance for understanding them.

2.1 Social Acceptance

Social acceptance as a concept has been understood in multitude of ways. The most commonly used conceptualisation comes from Wüstenhagen et al. (2007), who define the concept through three dimensions (community, socio-political, and market). This has been fundamental to much of the research in the field and which has been subject to conceptual development since then. This evolution has included debate on the concept and meta-analysis of the research field (Gaede & Rowlands, 2018, 2019; Wolsink, 2018, 2019). There also exists other valuable reviews of conceptual research on the social acceptance, such as (Batel, 2020), who argues that research on social acceptance of renewable energy technologies can be organized around three waves: 'normative' (how to overcome opposition, increase acceptance), 'criticism' (of RET projects; psychosocial impacts), and 'critical' (ideological assumptions of research and policy agendas; socio-political-ideological context; neoliberal capitalism).

Key papers that provide a guide to the concept of social acceptance include:

- Batel, S. (2020). Research on the social acceptance of renewable energy technologies: Past, present and future. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 68, 101544.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101544>
- Gaede, J., & Rowlands, I. H. (2018). Visualizing social acceptance research: A bibliometric review of the social acceptance literature for energy technology and fuels. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 40(December 2017), 142–158.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2017.12.006>
- Gaede, J., & Rowlands, I. H. (2019). The value of multiple perspectives: Problem-solving and critique in the evaluation of social acceptance research—A response to M. Wolsink. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 48 (December 2018), 262–268.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.12.007>
- Hübner, G., Leschinger, V., Müller, F. J., & Pohl, J. (2023). Broadening the social acceptance of wind energy—An Integrated Acceptance Model. *Energy Policy*, 173, 113360.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.113360>

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- Upham, P., Oltra, C. and Boso, À., (2015). Towards a cross-paradigmatic framework of the social acceptance of energy systems. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 8, pp.100-112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.05.003>
- Wolsink, M. (2019) Social acceptance revisited: gaps, questionable trends, and an auspicious perspective, *Energy Research and Social Science*. 46 (2018) 287–295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.07.034>.
- Wolsink, M (2019) Social acceptance, lost objects, and obsession with the 'public'—The pressing need for enhanced conceptual and methodological rigor, *Energy Research and Social Science* 48 (2019) 269–276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.12.006>.
- Wüstenhagen, R., Wolsink, M., & Bürer, M. J. (2007). Social acceptance of renewable energy innovation: An introduction to the concept. *Energy Policy*, 35(5), 2683–2691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.001>

2.2 Acceptability

'Acceptability' has emerged as an alternative to the core concept of social acceptance, as it appears to transcend a simple dichotomy of unacceptance/acceptance and provide a range of paths to socialisation. Some papers that are useful for familiarising with the concept of acceptability include:

- Fournis, Y., & Fortin, M. J. (2017). From social 'acceptance' to social 'acceptability' of wind energy projects: towards a territorial perspective. *Journal of environmental planning and management*, 60(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2015.1133406>.
- Lennon, B., Dunphy, N. P., & Sanvicente, E. (2019). Community acceptability and the energy transition: a citizens' perspective. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-019-0218-z>

2.3 Other Alternatives and Improvements to Social Acceptance

The field of social acceptance has been subject to a number of thematic debates. One of these relates to claims that there has been an over-emphasis of *community* acceptance and localised case studies, with the implication that more research should be done to combine the different dimensions of social acceptance and to adopt broader perspectives focusing on energy transition processes (Wolsink, 2019). The papers shown below provide insights into further alternative conceptualisations for social acceptance; indeed, the research conducted by MISTRAL researchers (see section 7), also highlights the wide range of concepts that can be usefully deployed in social acceptance research.

- Bell, D., Gray, T., Haggett, C. and Swaffield, J., (2013). Re-visiting the 'social gap': public opinion and relations of power in the local politics of wind energy. *Environmental Politics*, 22(1), pp.115-135. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2013.755793>
- Cohen, J.J., Reichl, J. and Schmidthaler, M., (2014). Re-focussing research efforts on the public acceptance of energy infrastructure: A critical review. *Energy*, 76, pp.4-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2013.12.056>

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- Hall, N.L., 2014. Can the “social licence to operate” concept enhance engagement and increase acceptance of renewable energy? A case study of wind farms in Australia. *Social Epistemology*, 28(3-4), pp.219-238.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02691728.2014.922636>
- Sovacool, B.K. and Ratan, P.L., (2012). Conceptualizing the acceptance of wind and solar electricity. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 16(7), pp.5268-5279.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.04.048>
- Wolsink, M. (2019). Social acceptance, lost objects, and obsession with the ‘public’—The pressing need for enhanced conceptual and methodological rigor. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 48, 269-276.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.12.006>

2.4 Opposition

Social acceptance research expanded rapidly in the early 2000’s in parallel with the growth of host community concerns with wind energy projects. As a result, much of the social acceptance research has focused on issue of *un*acceptance and local opposition. While much of this work offers descriptive accounts of community attitudes and seeks to identify the factors that may drive opposition, more reflective work has sought to understand the nature of the local conflicts, and place/community concerns within a broader context of transition and power.

- Aitken, M., McDonald, S., & Strachan, P. (2008). Locating ‘power’ in wind power planning processes: The (not so) influential role of local objectors. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 51(6), 777–99.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09640560802423566>
- Barry, J. and Ellis, G. (2011). “Beyond Consensus? Agonism, Republicanism and a Low Carbon Future.” In Devine-Wright P, ed. 2011. *Renewable Energy and the Public: from Nimby to Participation*. London, UK, Earthscan. 29 - 42. Available [here](#)
- Bidwell, D., (2013), The role of values in public beliefs and attitudes towards commercial wind energy. *Energy Policy*, 58, pp.189-199.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.03.010>
- Burningham, K., Barnett, J. and Walker, G., 2015. An array of deficits: unpacking NIMBY discourses in wind energy developers' conceptualizations of their local opponents. *Society & Natural Resources*, 28(3), pp.246–260.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2014.933923>
- Ellis, G., Barry, J. and Robinson, C., (2007) Many ways to say ‘no’, different ways to say ‘yes’: applying Q-methodology to understand public acceptance of wind farm proposals. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 50(4), pp.517-551.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09640560701402075>
- Hoen, B., Firestone, J., Rand, J., Elliot, D., Hübner, G., Pohl, J., Wisser, R., Lantz, E., Haac, T.R. and Kaliski, K., (2019). Attitudes of US wind turbine neighbors: analysis of a nationwide survey. *Energy Policy*, 134, p.110981.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.110981>

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- Lennon, M. and Scott, M., (2015). Contending Expertise: An Interpretive Approach to (Re) conceiving Wind Power's 'Planning Problem'. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 17(5), pp.593-616. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2014.1003349>
- Sovacool, B. K., Hess, D. J., Cantoni, R., Lee, D., Brisbois, M. C., Walnum, H. J., ... & Goel, S. (2022). Conflicted transitions: Exploring the actors, tactics, and outcomes of social opposition against energy infrastructure. *Global Environmental Change*, 73, 102473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2022.102473>

2.5 Place Attachment

Place attachment has been a key theme topic for understanding local community-development relationships. These papers provide a valuable introduction to this concept:

- Devine-Wright, P., (2005). Beyond NIMBYism: towards an integrated framework for understanding public perceptions of wind energy. *Wind Energy: An International Journal for Progress and Applications in Wind Power Conversion Technology*, 8(2), pp.125-139. <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.124>
- Devine-Wright, P. (2009). Rethinking NIMBYism: The role of place attachment and place identity in explaining place-protective action. *Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology*, 19(6), 426-441. <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.1004>
- Devine-Wright, P., & Howes, Y. (2010). Disruption to place attachment and the protection of restorative environments: A wind energy case study. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 30(3), 271-280 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2010.01.008>
- Devine-Wright, P., & Batel, S. (2017). My neighbourhood, my country or my planet? The influence of multiple place attachments and climate change concern on social acceptance of energy infrastructure. *Global Environmental Change*, 47, 110-120 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.08.003>
- Van Veelen, B. and Haggett, C., (2017). Uncommon ground: The role of different place attachments in explaining community renewable energy projects. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 57, pp.533-554. <https://doi.org/10.1111/soru.12128>

2.6 Defining 'affected' citizens and communities

Community acceptance and a focus on local arenas have been an important focus of social acceptance research. A key issue has been the definition and identification of those communities that are 'affected' by a wind energy project and the following papers offer insight into this issue:

- Cowell, C., Bristow, G. and Munday, M (2011) Acceptance, acceptability and environmental justice: the role of community benefits in wind energy development, *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 54:4, 539-557, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2010.521047>

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- Devine-Wright, P., & Sherry-Brennan, F. (2019). Where do you draw the line? Legitimacy and fairness in constructing community benefit fund boundaries for energy infrastructure projects. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 54, 166-175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.04.002>
- Hoen, B., Wiser, R., Cappers, P., Thayer, M. and Sethi, G., (2011). Wind energy facilities and residential properties: the effect of proximity and view on sales prices. *Journal of Real Estate Research*, 33(3), pp.279-316. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10835547.2011.12091307>
- Hübner, G., Pohl, J., Hoen, B., Firestone, J., Rand, J., Elliott, D. and Haac, R., (2019), Monitoring annoyance and stress effects of wind turbines on nearby residents: A comparison of US and European samples. *Environment international*, 132, p.105090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.105090>
- Jones, C.R. and Eiser, J.R., 2010. Understanding 'local' opposition to wind development in the UK: how big is a backyard?. *Energy Policy*, 38(6), pp.3106-3117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.01.051>
- Simcock, N., 2014. Exploring how stakeholders in two community wind projects use a "those affected" principle to evaluate the fairness of each project's spatial boundary. *Local Environment*, 19(3), pp.241-258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2013.788482>

2.7 Justice and participation

Many of the issues that underlie community acceptance relate to different perceptions of justice, particularly distributional and procedural justice, and link to wider conceptions of justice, at different scales, that arise from of the energy transition (Jenkins et al., 2014). This research is a rapidly emerging area of research, and examples of this work includes:

- Aitken, M. (2009). Wind Power Planning Controversies and the Construction of 'Expert' and 'Lay' Knowledges. *Science as Culture*, 18:1, 47-64, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09505430802385682>
- Cowell, R., Bristow, G. and Munday, M., (2012), *Wind energy and justice for disadvantaged communities*. York: Joseph Rowntree Foundation. Available [here](#).
- Elmallah, S. and Rand, J., 2022. "After the leases are signed, it's a done deal": Exploring procedural injustices for utility-scale wind energy planning in the United States. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 89, p.102549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102549>
- Roddis, P., Carver, S., Dallimer, M., Norman, P., & Ziv, G. (2018). The role of community acceptance in planning outcomes for onshore wind and solar farms: An energy justice analysis. *Applied Energy*, 226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.05.087>
- Simcock, N., (2016), Procedural justice and the implementation of community wind energy projects: A case study from South Yorkshire, UK. *Land Use Policy*, 59, pp.467-477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.08.034>
- Sovacool, B. K., Martiskainen, M., Hook, A., & Baker, L. (2019). Decarbonization and its discontents: a critical energy justice perspective on four low-carbon transitions. *Climatic Change* (Vol. 155, Issue 4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-019-02521-7>
- Suškevičs, M., Eiter, S., Martinat, S., Stober, D., Vollmer, E., de Boer, C. L., & Buchecker, M. (2019). Regional variation in public acceptance of wind energy development in Europe: What

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are the roles of planning procedures and participation?. *Land use policy*, 81, 311-323.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2018.10.032>

- Velasco-Herrejon, P. and Bauwens, T., (2020). Energy justice from the bottom up: A capability approach to community acceptance of wind energy in Mexico. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 70, p.101711. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101711>
- Walker, C., & Baxter, J. (2017). Procedural justice in Canadian wind energy development: A comparison of community-based and technocratic siting processes. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 29, 160-169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2017.05.016>
- Wolsink, M. (2007). Planning of renewables schemes: Deliberative and fair decision-making on landscape issues instead of reproachful accusations of non-cooperation. *Energy Policy*, 35(5), 2692-2704. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.002>

2.8 Dynamics of social acceptance

A long-standing criticism of social acceptance research is that it has mostly been based on 'snapshot' research, with a particular emphasis on pre-construction or pre-consent stages. Yet is it commonly acknowledged as a dynamic concept, which can be understood in a number of ways. The papers below have been highlighted as a useful introduction to the dynamic nature of social acceptance, although this is an area of emerging research, including being the topic of a forthcoming Special Issue of *Energy Policy* (2023) featuring several papers from MISTRAL researchers, some papers from which are included here and in section 7:

- Cuppen, E., Ejderyan, O., Pesch, U., Spruit, S., van de Grift, E., Correljé, A., & Taebi, B. (2020). When controversies cascade: Analysing the dynamics of public engagement and conflict in the Netherlands and Switzerland through "controversy spillover". *Energy Research & Social Science*, 68, 101593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101593>
- Devine-Wright, P., Batel, S., Aas, O., Sovacool, B., LaBelle, M. C., & Ruud, A. (2017). A conceptual framework for understanding the social acceptance of energy infrastructure: Insights from energy storage. *Energy Policy*, 107, 27–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.04.020>
- Eltham, D. C., Harrison, G. P., & Allen, S. J. (2008). Change in public attitudes towards a Cornish wind farm: Implications for planning. *Energy Policy*, 36(1), 23-33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2007.09.010>
- Frantál, B., (2015), Have local government and public expectations of wind energy project benefits been met? Implications for repowering schemes. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 17(2), pp.217-236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2014.936583>
- Küpers, S. and Batel S. (forthcoming) Time, History and Meaning Making in Research on People's Relations with Renewable Energy Technology (RET) Projects – A Conceptual Proposal, *Energy Policy*
- Maruyama, Y., Nishikido, M. and Iida, T., (2007),. The rise of community wind power in Japan: Enhanced acceptance through social innovation. *Energy Policy*, 35(5), pp.2761-2769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.010>

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- Mills, S. B., Bessette, D., & Smith, H. (2019). Exploring landowners' post-construction changes in perceptions of wind energy in Michigan. *Land Use Policy*, 82, 754-762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.01.010>
- Windemer, R., (2023). Acceptance should not be assumed. How the dynamics of social acceptance changes over time, impacting onshore wind repowering. *Energy Policy*, 173, p.113363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.113363>
- Wolsink, M. (2007). Wind power implementation: the nature of public attitudes: equity and fairness instead of 'backyard motives'. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 11(6), 1188-1207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2005.10.005>

2.9 Concepts for socio-political-ideological contexts: frames, imaginaries and orders of worth

The meaning, measurement, and applicability of the concept of social acceptance (or acceptability) of renewable energy projects is still very much a contested concept, which is influenced by how wind energy projects and their perceived impacts are subjectively framed by a wide range of stakeholders and interests. There is a diverse literature that explores issues of framing and how this can influence response and understanding of wind energy projects and other related issues.

- Bidwell, D., (2013), The role of values in public beliefs and attitudes towards commercial wind energy. *Energy Policy*, 58, pp.189-199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.03.010>
- Cass, N. and Walker, G., (2009), Emotion and rationality: The characterisation and evaluation of opposition to renewable energy projects. *Emotion, Space and Society*, 2(1), pp.62-69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emospa.2009.05.006>
- Chateau, Z., Devine-Wright, P. and Wills, J., (2021), Integrating sociotechnical and spatial imaginaries in researching energy futures. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 80, p.102207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102207>
- Ellis, G., Barry, J. and Robinson, C., 2007. Many ways to say 'no', different ways to say 'yes': applying Q-methodology to understand public acceptance of wind farm proposals. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 50(4), pp.517-551. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640560701402075>
- Karakislak, I., Hildebrand, J. and Schweizer-Ries, P., (2021), Exploring the interaction between social norms and perceived justice of wind energy projects: A qualitative analysis. *Journal of Environmental Policy and Planning*, pp.1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2021.2020631>
- Longhurst, N. and Chilvers, J., 2019. Mapping diverse visions of energy transitions: co-producing sociotechnical imaginaries. *Sustainability Science*, 14(4), pp.973-990. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-019-00702-y>
- Wolsink, M. (2020). Framing in renewable energy policies: a glossary. *Energies*, 13(11), 2871. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13112871>
- Wolsink, M. and Breukers, S., 2010. Contrasting the core beliefs regarding the effective implementation of wind power. An international study of stakeholder perspectives. *Journal of*

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Environmental Planning and Management, 53(5), pp.535-558.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09640561003633581>

3. Research Design

Social acceptance research has not only engaged with a diverse range of concepts, some of which are noted above, but also sought to address a very large number of research questions, demanding varied research designs and methods. Some of the studies that have used different methodological approaches are described in this section.

3.1 Case Studies

The use of single case studies of how communities have responded to a proposed or constructed wind energy project (particularly using household surveys), have been the most common research design in this field, and a few examples are noted here. This approach has been very valuable in developing a broad understanding of the impact of specific socio-cultural contexts, projects designs and other variables that can shape social acceptance. There has however, been little consistency in the variables used in each case, not the way common variables are measured (for example in relation to proximity), although the survey instrument used by [Berkeley Labs](#), is increasingly recognised as a key baseline instrument. There are examples of comparative case studies, case studies that have used different types of approaches or survey instruments, and a range of other research designs, examples of which are included below.

- Hall, N., Ashworth, P. and Devine-Wright, P., (2013). Societal acceptance of wind farms: Analysis of four common themes across Australian case studies. *Energy Policy*, 58, pp.200-208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.03.009>
- Khorsand, I., Kormos, C., MacDonald, E.G. and Crawford, C., 2015. Wind energy in the city: An interurban comparison of social acceptance of wind energy projects. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 8, pp.66-77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.04.008>
- Motosu, M., & Maruyama, Y. (2016). Local acceptance by people with unvoiced opinions living close to a wind farm: A case study from Japan. *Energy Policy*, 91, 362-370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.01.018>
- Segreto, M., Principe, L., Desormeaux, A., Torre, M., Tomassetti, L., Tratzi, P., Paolini, V. and Petracchini, F., (2020). Trends in social acceptance of renewable energy across Europe—A literature review. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(24), p.9161. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17249161>
- Warren, C.R. and McFadyen, M., (2010). Does community ownership affect public attitudes to wind energy? A case study from south-west Scotland. *Land use policy*, 27(2), pp.204-213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2008.12.010>
- Walker, C., Baxter, J., & Ouellette, D. (2014). Beyond rhetoric to understanding determinants of wind turbine support and conflict in two Ontario, Canada communities. *Environment and Planning A*, 46(3), 730-745. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a130004>

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- Yuan, X., Zuo, J. and Huisingh, D., 2015. Social acceptance of wind power: a case study of Shandong Province, China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 92, pp.168-178.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.12.097>
- Zoellner, J., Schweizer-Ries, P., & Wemheuer, C. (2008). Public acceptance of renewable energies: Results from case studies in Germany. *Energy Policy*, 36(11), 4136–4141.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2008.06.026>

3.2 Longitudinal studies

While the predominant approach to social acceptance research has been through different forms of case study, there has been a very limited number of longitudinal research despite several calls for such an approach to better highlight the dynamic features of social acceptance (e.g. Ellis and Ferraro 2016, Baxter et al., 2020). Some of the studies that have engaged with, or undertaken longitudinal research, are noted below.

- Dermont, C., Ingold, K., Kammermann, L., & Stadelmann-Steffen, I. (2017). Bringing the policy making perspective in: A political science approach to social acceptance. *Energy policy*, 108, 359-368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.05.062>
- Firestone, J., Hirt, C., Bidwell, D., Gardner, M., & Dwyer, J. (2020). Faring well in offshore wind power siting? Trust, engagement and process fairness in the United States. *Energy Research and Social Science*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101393>
- Parkhill, K. A., Shirani, F., Butler, C., Henwood, K. L., Groves, C., & Pidgeon, N. F. (2015). "We are a community [but] that takes a certain amount of energy": Exploring shared visions, social action, and resilience in place-based community-led energy initiatives. *Environmental Science and Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.05.014>

3.3 'Representative' national samples

A further approach that has complemented the case study approach has been those studies that have explored national level data in relation to public attitudes and other variables that are relevant to understanding social acceptance. Some of the studies that have attempted to capture national insights are noted below.

- Cousse, J., Wüstenhagen, R., & Schneider, N. (2020). Mixed feelings on wind energy: Affective imagery and local concern driving social acceptance in Switzerland. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 70, 101676.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101676>
- Hoen, B., Firestone, J., Rand, J., Elliot, D., Hübner, G., Pohl, J., Wisser, R., Lantz, E., Haac, T.R. and Kaliski, K., 2019. Attitudes of US wind turbine neighbors: analysis of a nationwide survey. *Energy Policy*, 134, p.110981.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.110981>

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- Russell, A., & Firestone, J. (2021). What's love got to do with it? Understanding local cognitive and affective responses to wind power projects. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 71, 101833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101833>
- Sonnberger, M., & Ruddat, M. (2017). Local and socio-political acceptance of wind farms in Germany. *Technology in Society*, 51, 56-65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2017.07.005>
- Walter, G. (2014). Determining the local acceptance of wind energy projects in Switzerland: The importance of general attitudes and project characteristics. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 4, 78-88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2014.09.003>

3.4 Capturing Community Opinions

Capturing of community opinions has been a core source of evidence in developing insights into social acceptance issues around wind energy projects, and these have used a variety of methodological approaches, a number of which are provided below as examples:

- Bidwell, D. (2013). The role of values in public beliefs and attitudes towards commercial wind energy. *Energy Policy*, 58, 189-199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.03.010>
- Eltham, D. C., Harrison, G. P., & Allen, S. J. (2008). Change in public attitudes towards a Cornish wind farm: Implications for planning. *Energy Policy*, 36(1), 23-33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2007.09.010>
- Hoen, B., Firestone, J., Rand, J., Elliot, D., Hübner, G., Pohl, J., Wiser, R., Lantz, E., Haac, T.R. and Kaliski, K., (2019), Attitudes of US wind turbine neighbors: analysis of a nationwide survey. *Energy Policy*, 134, p.110981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.110981>
- Musall, F. D., & Kuik, O. (2011). Local acceptance of renewable energy—A case study from southeast Germany. *Energy Policy*, 39(6), 3252-3260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.03.017>
- Swofford, J., & Slattery, M. (2010). Public attitudes of wind energy in Texas: Local communities in close proximity to wind farms and their effect on decision-making. *Energy Policy*, 38(5), 2508-2519. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.12.046>
- Warren, C. R., & McFadyen, M. (2010). Does community ownership affect public attitudes to wind energy? A case study from south-west Scotland. *Land Use Policy*, 27(2), 204-213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2008.12.010>

3.5 Qualitative methods

Due to the complexity of some of the factors influencing social acceptance of energy projects, and the variety of research questions that have been asking in relation to this topic, it is unsurprising that a wide range of research methods and designs have been used within the field. The studies noted below provide some examples of where studies have been primarily undertaken using qualitative methods.

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- Caporale, D., Sangiorgio, V., Amodio, A., & De Lucia, C. (2020). Multi-criteria and focus group analysis for social acceptance of wind energy. *Energy Policy*, 140, 111387.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111387>
- Friedl, C., & Reichl, J. (2016). Realizing energy infrastructure projects—A qualitative empirical analysis of local practices to address social acceptance. *Energy Policy*, 89, 184-193.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2015.11.027>
- Jørgensen, M. L., Anker, H. T., & Lassen, J. (2020). Distributive fairness and local acceptance of wind turbines: The role of compensation schemes. *Energy Policy*, 138, 111294.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111294>
- Karakislak, I., Hildebrand, J., & Schweizer-Ries, P. (2021). Exploring the interaction between social norms and perceived justice of wind energy projects: A qualitative analysis. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 1-14.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2021.2020631>
- Langer, K., Decker, T., Roosen, J., & Menrad, K. (2016). A qualitative analysis to understand the acceptance of wind energy in Bavaria. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 64, 248-259.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.05.084>
- Ruggiero, S., Onkila, T. and Kuittinen, V., (2014) Realizing the social acceptance of community renewable energy: A process-outcome analysis of stakeholder influence. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 4, pp.53-63.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2014.09.001>
- Scherhauser, P., Höltinger, S., Salak, B., Schauppenlehner, T. and Schmidt, J., (2017). Patterns of acceptance and non-acceptance within energy landscapes: A case study on wind energy expansion in Austria. *Energy Policy*, 109, pp.863-870.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.05.057>
- Sovacool, B. K., & Ratan, P. L. (2012). Conceptualizing the acceptance of wind and solar electricity. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 16(7), 5268-5279.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.04.048>
- Strazzer, E., Mura, M., & Contu, D. (2012). Combining choice experiments with psychometric scales to assess the social acceptability of wind energy projects: A latent class approach. *Energy Policy*, 48, 334-347.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.05.037>

3.6 Quantitative Methods

The studies noted below provide some examples of where studies have been primarily undertaken using quantitative methods.

- Cousse, J., Wüstenhagen, R., & Schneider, N. (2020). Mixed feelings on wind energy: Affective imagery and local concern driving social acceptance in Switzerland. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 70, 101676.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101676>

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- Hoen, B., Firestone, J., Rand, J., Elliot, D., Hübner, G., Pohl, J., Wisser, R., Lantz, E., Haac, T.R. and Kaliski, K., (2019), Attitudes of US wind turbine neighbors: analysis of a nationwide survey. *Energy Policy*, 134, p.110981.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.110981>
- Paravantis, J. A., Stigka, E., Mihalakakou, G., Michalena, E., Hills, J. M., & Dourmas, V. (2018). Social acceptance of renewable energy projects: A contingent valuation investigation in Western Greece. *Renewable Energy*, 123, 639-651.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.02.068>
- Seidl, R., von Wirth, T., & Krütli, P. (2019). Social acceptance of distributed energy systems in Swiss, German, and Austrian energy transitions. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 54, 117–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.04.006>
- Sonberger, M., & Ruddat, M. (2017). Local and socio-political acceptance of wind farms in Germany. *Technology in Society*, 51, 56-65.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2017.07.005>
- Stigka, E.K., Paravantis, J.A. and Mihalakakou, G.K., (2014),. Social acceptance of renewable energy sources: A review of contingent valuation applications. *Renewable and sustainable energy Reviews*, 32, pp.100-106.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.12.026>
- Van der Horst, D. and Toke, D., 2010. Exploring the landscape of wind farm developments; local area characteristics and planning process outcomes in rural England. *Land Use Policy*, 27(2), pp.214-221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2009.05.006>
- Vespa, M., Kortsch, T., Hildebrand, J., Schweizer-Ries, P. and Volkmer, S.A., 2022. Not All Places Are Equal: Using Instagram to Understand Cognitions and Affect towards Renewable Energy Infrastructures. *Sustainability*, 14(7), p.4071.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su14074071>
- Walker, B.J., Wiersma, B. and Bailey, E., (2014) Community benefits, framing and the social acceptance of offshore wind farms: an experimental study in England. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 3, pp.46-54.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2014.07.003>

3.7 Mixed and novel methods

There are also many studies that have adopted a mixed methods approach, with some examples listed below.

- Allen, J., & Jones, S. P. (2012). Tilting at Windmills in a changing climate: a performative walking practice and dance-documentary film as an embodied mode of engagement and persuasion. *Research in Drama Education: The Journal of Applied Theatre and Performance*, 17(2), 209-227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13569783.2012.670423>
- Borch, K., Munk, A. K., & Dahlgaard, V. (2020). Mapping wind-power controversies on social media: Facebook as a powerful mobilizer of local resistance. *Energy Policy*, 138, 111223.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.111223>

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- Caporale, D., Sangiorgio, V., Amodio, A. and De Lucia, C., (2020). Multi-criteria and focus group analysis for social acceptance of wind energy. *Energy Policy*, 140, p.111387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111387>
- Haggett, C. and Toke, D., 2006. Crossing the great divide—using multi-method analysis to understand opposition to windfarms. *Public Administration*, 84(1), pp.103-120. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0033-3298.2006.00495.x>
- Li, R., Crowe, J., Leifer, D., Zou, L., & Schoof, J. (2019). Beyond big data: Social media challenges and opportunities for understanding social perception of energy. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 56, 101217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101217>
- Velasco-Herrejon, P., & Bauwens, T. (2020). Energy justice from the bottom up: A capability approach to community acceptance of wind energy in Mexico. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 70, 101711. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101711>
- Walker, C. and Baxter, J., (2019). Method sequence and dominance in mixed methods research: A case study of the social acceptance of wind energy literature. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 18, p.1609406919834379. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406919834379>
- Walker, C., Stephenson, L., & Baxter, J. (2018). "His main platform is 'stop the turbines'": Political discourse, partisanship and local responses to wind energy in Canada. *Energy Policy*, 123, 670-681. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.08.046>
- Zoellner, J., Schweizer-Ries, P., & Wemheuer, C. (2008). Public acceptance of renewable energies: Results from case studies in Germany. *Energy Policy*, 36(11), 4136-4141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2008.06.026>

3.8 Critical Research Approaches

Some research in this field links issues of acceptance to power dynamics across society or draws attention to the needs to transform the energy system or even wide social structures of which it is a part. Such studies engage a range of alternative conceptual frames and methods, some of which are highlighted below.

- Barry, J., Ellis, G., & Robinson, C. (2008). Cool rationalities and hot air: a rhetorical approach to understanding debates on renewable energy. *Global Environmental Politics*, 8(2), 67-98. <https://doi.org/10.1162/glep.2008.8.2.67>
- Batel, S. (2020). Research on the social acceptance of renewable energy technologies: Past, present and future. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 68, 101544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101544>
- Batel, S., & Rudolph, D. (2021). Contributions, tensions and future avenues of a critical approach to the social acceptance of renewable energy infrastructures, chapter in 'A critical approach to the social acceptance of renewable energy infrastructures' (pp. 237-257). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73699-6_13

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- Bosch, S., & Schmidt, M. (2020). Wonderland of technology? How energy landscapes reveal inequalities and injustices of the German Energiewende. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 70, 101733. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101733>
- Cowell, R., & Devine-Wright, P. (2018). A 'delivery-democracy dilemma'? Mapping and explaining policy change for public engagement with energy infrastructure. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 20(4), 499-517. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2018.1443005>
- Cuppen, E. (2018). The value of social conflicts. Critiquing invited participation in energy projects. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 38, 28-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.01.016c>
- Kropp, C. (2018). Controversies around energy landscapes in third modernity. *Landscape research*, 43(4), 562-573. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01426397.2017.1287890>
- Vasstrøm, M., & Lysgård, H. K. (2021). What shapes Norwegian wind power policy? Analysing the constructing forces of policymaking and emerging questions of energy justice. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 77, 102089. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102089>

3.9 Inter-Disciplinary Studies

Energy transition as a challenge is interlinked with the decarbonisation of other systems. It is also a challenge that reaches out throughout society; and requires socio-technical transformation. Therefore, research on the topic area is often interdisciplinary. Here, we introduce some examples of interdisciplinary research related to social acceptance and the energy transition.

- Batel, S., Devine-Wright, P., Wold, L., Egeland, H., Jacobsen, G., & Aas, O. (2015). The role of (de-) essentialisation within siting conflicts: An interdisciplinary approach. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 44, 149–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2015.10.004>
- Haggett, C. (2021). Social Acceptance and Interdisciplinarity: Understanding the Constructive Power of Terminology. In *A critical approach to the social acceptance of renewable energy infrastructures* (pp. 123-139). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73699-6>
- Kirkegaard, J. K., & Nyborg, S. (2021) ANT Perspective on Wind Power Planning and Social Acceptance-A Call for Interdisciplinarity. In *A critical approach to the social acceptance of renewable energy infrastructures* (p105-121). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73699-6_6
- Korjonen-Kuusipuro, K., Hujala, M., Pätäri, S., Bergman, J. P., & Olkkonen, L. (2017). The emergence and diffusion of grassroots energy innovations: Building an interdisciplinary approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 140, 1156–1164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.10.047>

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- McCauley, D., Ramasar, V., Heffron, R. J., Sovacool, B. K., Mebratu, D., & Mundaca, L. (2019). Energy justice in the transition to low carbon energy systems: Exploring key themes in interdisciplinary research. *Applied Energy*, 233, 916-921.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.10.005>
- Sovacool, B. K., Axsen, J., & Sorrell, S. (2018). Promoting novelty, rigor, and style in energy social science: Towards codes of practice for appropriate methods and research design. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 45, 12-42.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.07.007>
- Spiess, H., Lobsiger-Kägi, E., Carabias-Hütter, V., & Marcolla, A. (2015). Future acceptance of wind energy production: Exploring future local acceptance of wind energy production in a Swiss alpine region. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 101, 263-274.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2015.06.042>

4. Communities of Interest

A vast range of stakeholders are involved in the energy transition, and many different actors may have relevance to understanding the different processes, structures, and project. Therefore, social acceptance research includes many communities of interest. A number of the key categories of actors are included here.

4.1 Geographies of 'concern' in social acceptance?

An interesting question in social acceptance research has been the parties who should be considered as being impacted or who should have a say in debates around specific wind energy projects. The research below are examples that have explored this issue.

- Jones, C. R., & Eiser, J. R. (2010). Understanding 'local' opposition to wind development in the UK: how big is a backyard? *Energy Policy*, 38(6), 3106-3117.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.01.051>
- Pesch, U. (2019). Elusive publics in energy projects: The politics of localness and energy democracy. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 56, 101225.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101225>
- Simcock, N. (2014). Exploring how stakeholders in two community wind projects use a "those affected" principle to evaluate the fairness of each project's spatial boundary. *Local Environment*, 19(3), 241-258.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2013.788482>
- Solman, H., Smits, M., van Vliet, B., & Bush, S. (2021). Co-production in the wind energy sector: A systematic literature review of public engagement beyond invited stakeholder participation. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 72, 101876.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101876>
- van de Grift, E., & Cuppen, E. (2022). Beyond the public in controversies: A systematic review on social opposition and renewable energy actors. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 91, 102749.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102749>

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4.2 Local residents and other 'community' interests

- Bidwell, D. (2013). The role of values in public beliefs and attitudes towards commercial wind energy. *Energy Policy*, 58, 189-199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.03.010>
- Firestone, J., Hoen, B., Rand, J., Elliott, D., Hübner, G., & Pohl, J. (2018). Reconsidering barriers to wind power projects: community engagement, developer transparency and place. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 20(3), 370-386. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2017.1418656>
- Motosu, M., & Maruyama, Y. (2016). Local acceptance by people with unvoiced opinions living close to a wind farm: A case study from Japan. *Energy Policy*, 91, 362-370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.01.018>
- Swofford, J., & Slattery, M. (2010). Public attitudes of wind energy in Texas: Local communities in close proximity to wind farms and their effect on decision-making. *Energy Policy*, 38(5), 2508-2519. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.12.046>
- Walker, C., Stephenson, L., & Baxter, J. (2018). "His main platform is 'stop the turbines'": Political discourse, partisanship and local responses to wind energy in Canada. *Energy Policy*, 123, 670-681.. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.08.046>

4.3 Activist Groups

- Crawford, J., Bessette, D., & Mills, S. B. (2022). Rallying the anti-crowd: Organized opposition, democratic deficit, and a potential social gap in large-scale solar energy. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 90, 102597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102597>
- Galvin, R. (2018). Trouble at the end of the line: local activism and social acceptance in low-carbon electricity transmission in Lower Franconia, Germany. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 38, 114-126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.01.022>
- Ogilvie, M., & Rootes, C. (2015). The impact of local campaigns against wind energy developments. *Environmental Politics*, 24(6), 874-893. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2015.1063301>
- Sovacool, B. K., Hess, D. J., Cantoni, R., Lee, D., Brisbois, M. C., Walnum, H. J., ... & Goel, S. (2022). Conflicted transitions: Exploring the actors, tactics, and outcomes of social opposition against energy infrastructure. *Global Environmental Change*, 73, 102473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2022.102473>

4.4 Developers, financiers and owners of wind energy projects

- Baxter, J., Walker, C., Ellis, G., Devine-Wright, P., Adams, M., & Fullerton, R. S. (2020). Scale, history and justice in community wind energy: An empirical review. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 68, 101532. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101532>
- Burningham, K., Barnett, J., & Walker, G. (2015). An array of deficits: unpacking NIMBY discourses in wind energy developers' conceptualizations of their local opponents. *Society & Natural Resources*, 28(3), 246-260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2014.933923>

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- Côté, E., Đukan, M., Pons-Seres de Brauwer, C., & Wüstenhagen, R. (2022). The price of actor diversity: Measuring project developers' willingness to accept risks in renewable energy auctions. *Energy Policy*, 163, [112835].
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.112835>
- de Brauwer, C. P. S., & Cohen, J. J. (2020). Analysing the potential of citizen-financed community renewable energy to drive Europe's low-carbon energy transition. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 133, 110300.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110300>
- Ebers Broughel, A., Hampl, N., 2018. Community financing of renewable energy projects in Austria and Switzerland: Profiles of potential investors. *Energy Policy* 123, 722–736.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.08.054>
- Landeta-Manzano, B., Arana-Landin, G., Calvo, P.M., & Heras-Saizarbitoria, I. 2018. Wind energy and local communities: A manufacturer's efforts to gain acceptance. *Energy Policy*, 121: 314-324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.05.034>
- Mey, F., & Diesendorf, M. (2018). Who owns an energy transition? Strategic action fields and community wind energy in Denmark. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 35, 108-117.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2017.10.044>
- Polzin, F. (2017). Mobilizing private finance for low-carbon innovation—A systematic review of barriers and solutions. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 77, 525-535.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.04.007>
- Raven, R. P., Mourik, R. M., Feenstra, C. F. J., & Heiskanen, E. (2009). Modulating societal acceptance in new energy projects: towards a toolkit methodology for project managers. *Energy*, 34(5), 564-574. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2008.08.012>

4.5 Consenting and Regulating Authorities

Planning processes are important for many elements of social acceptance, such as regulating the location and scale of projects, or encouraging public participation in consenting decisions. Papers below show examples of social acceptance discussion in relation to consenting and regulating authorities.

- Agterbosch, S., Meertens, R. M., & Vermeulen, W. J. (2009). The relative importance of social and institutional conditions in the planning of wind power projects. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 13(2), 393-405.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2007.10.010>
- Bout, C., Gregg, J. S., Haselip, J., & Ellis, G. (2021). How Is Social Acceptance Reflected in National Renewable Energy Plans? Evidence from Three Wind-Rich Countries. *Energies*, 14(13), 3999. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14133999>
- Breukers, S., & Wolsink, M. (2007). Wind power implementation in changing institutional landscapes: An international comparison. *Energy Policy*, 35(5), 2737-2750.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.004>

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- Ellis, G., Cowell, R., Warren, C., Strachan, P., Szarka, J., Hadwin, R., ... & Nadai, A. (2009). Wind Power: Is There A "Planning Problem"? *Planning Theory and Practice*, 10(4) 521-547
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14649350903441555>
- Zaunbrecher, B. S., & Ziefle, M. (2016). Integrating acceptance-relevant factors into wind power planning: A discussion. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 27, 307–314.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2016.08.018>

4.6 Landowners

As siting decisions are important elements of social acceptance of a project, the role of landowners as key stakeholders is an impactful element of the energy transition processes. Research below works as an introduction into landowners as stakeholders.

- Chandrashekeran, S. (2021). Rent and reparation: how the law shapes Indigenous opportunities from large renewable energy projects. *Local Environment*, 26(3), 379-396.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2020.1861590>
- Copena, D., & Simón, X. (2018). Wind farms and payments to landowners: Opportunities for rural development for the case of Galicia. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 95, 38-47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.06.043>
- Jacquet, J. B. (2012). Landowner attitudes toward natural gas and wind farm development in northern Pennsylvania. *Energy Policy*, 50, 677-688.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.08.011>
- Jacquet, J. B. (2015). The rise of "private participation" in the planning of energy projects in the rural United States. *Society & Natural Resources*, 28(3), 231-245.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2014.945056>
- Koelman, M., Hartmann, T., & Spit, T. J. (2022). It's not all about the money—landowner motivation and high voltage grid development. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2022.2093175>

4.7 Other Types of Stakeholders

As highlighted in the beginning of this section, the range of stakeholders relevant for social acceptance research and the energy transition is vast. Articles below elaborate on less well-known stakeholders.

- Aitken, M. (2009). Wind power planning controversies and the construction of 'expert' and 'lay' knowledges. *Science as culture*, 18(1), 47-64.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09505430802385682>
- Busch, H., & McCormick, K. (2014). Local power: exploring the motivations of mayors and key success factors for local municipalities to go 100% renewable energy. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 4(1), 1-15.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/2192-0567-4-5>

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5. Local Impacts

Social acceptance research has also sought to understand the nature of impacts caused by wind energy projects, and how these may affect host communities and the wider environment. Some examples from these fields of research are included here.

5.1 Psychosocial Impacts

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5.2 Noise and annoyance

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5.3 Biodiversity

- Arnett, E. B., & Baerwald, E. F. (2013). Impacts of wind energy development on bats: implications for conservation. In *Bat evolution, ecology, and conservation* (pp. 435-456). Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-7397-8_21
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6. Project Characteristics

Renewable energy projects are becoming increasingly diverse, ranging in type of technology, size, ownership, and other features. These project characteristics bring their own variables to social acceptance of renewable energy research.

6.1 Types of Technology

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6.2 Project Scale

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6.3 Project Location

Connected to the scale of projects, also project location has been a significant variable for social acceptance research. It has even been argued that siting decision is the most important decision for acceptance of renewable energy developments.

- Cowell, R. (2010). Wind power, landscape and strategic, spatial planning—the construction of ‘acceptable locations’ in Wales. *Land Use Policy*, 27(2), 222-232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2009.01.006>
- Devine-Wright, P., & Wiersma, B. (2020). Understanding community acceptance of a potential offshore wind energy project in different locations: An island-based analysis of ‘place-technology fit’. *Energy Policy*, 137, 111086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.111086>
- Ek, K., & Persson, L. (2014). Wind farms—Where and how to place them? A choice experiment approach to measure consumer preferences for characteristics of wind farm establishments in Sweden. *Ecological economics*, 105, 193-203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2014.06.001>
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- Rudolph, D., Kirkegaard, J., Lyhne, I., Clausen, N. E., & Kørnø, L. (2017). Spoiled darkness? Sense of place and annoyance over obstruction lights from the world’s largest wind turbine test centre in Denmark. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 25, 80–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2016.12.024>

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6.4 Community Energy and other ownership Models

Another key variable is ownership. Research on this topic has focused on questions such as community ownership, and landowners as stakeholders. These discussions are elaborated in the literature below.

- Bauwens, T., & Devine-Wright, P. (2018). Positive energies? An empirical study of community energy participation and attitudes to renewable energy. *Energy Policy*, 118, 612-625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.03.062>
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- Gorroño-Albizu, L., Sperling, K., & Djørup, S. (2019). The past, present and uncertain future of community energy in Denmark: Critically reviewing and conceptualising citizen ownership. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 57, 101231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101231>.
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- Hogan, J. L., Warren, C. R., Simpson, M., & McCauley, D. (2022). What makes local energy projects acceptable? Probing the connection between ownership structures and community acceptance. *Energy Policy*, 171, 113257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.113257>
- Rommel, J., Radtke, J., Von Jorck, G., Mey, F., & Yildiz, Ö. (2018). Community renewable energy at a crossroads: A think piece on degrowth, technology, and the democratization of the German energy system. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 197, 1746-1753. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.11.114>
- Schumacher, K., Krones, F., McKenna, R., & Schultmann, F. (2019). Public acceptance of renewable energies and energy autonomy: A comparative study in the French, German and Swiss Upper Rhine region. *Energy Policy*, 126, 315-332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.11.032>
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- Walker, C., & Baxter, J. (2017). "It's easy to throw rocks at a corporation": wind energy development and distributive justice in Canada. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 19(6), 754-768. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2016.1267614>
- Warren, C. R., & McFadyen, M. (2010). Does community ownership affect public attitudes to wind energy? A case study from south-west Scotland. *Land Use Policy*, 27(2), 204-213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2008.12.010>

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6.5 Financial Participation and community benefits

Financial participation of the public in energy projects is an important element of the energy transition and social acceptance. This participation can take for example the form of shared ownership or community benefits, which has gained much research attention.

- Aitken, M. (2010). Wind power and community benefits: Challenges and opportunities. *Energy policy*, 38(10), 6066-6075.
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- Evans, B., Parks, J., & Theobald, K. (2011). Urban wind power and the private sector: Community benefits, social acceptance and public engagement. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 54(2), 227-244.
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7. MISTRAL Research

The goal of the MISTRAL-ITN has been to train the next generation of researchers to find solutions on social acceptance and energy transition challenges. A natural outcome of this goal has been that MISTRAL researchers have developed new ways to understand social acceptance issues and the concept itself, advancing the understanding of the energy transition. Some of the publications that have been produced from the project are listed below, with an updated list maintained at <https://mistral-itn.eu/>.

- Pons-Seres de Brauwer, C., & Cohen, J. J. (2022). Citizen preferences for co-investing in renewable energy: an empirical exploration of the “community-as-investor” acceptance of renewables’ innovation. In *Energy transition in the Baltic Sea region: understanding stakeholder engagement and community acceptance*/edited by Farid Karimi and Michael Rodi (pp. 61-89).. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781032003092-7>
- de Brauwer, C. P. S., & Cohen, J. J. (2020). Analysing the potential of citizen-financed community renewable energy to drive Europe's low-carbon energy transition. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 133, 110300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110300>
- Chateau, Z., Devine-Wright, P., & Wills, J. (2021). Integrating sociotechnical and spatial imaginaries in researching energy futures. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 80, 102207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102207>
- Côté, E., Đukan, M., de Brauwer, C. P. S., & Wüstenhagen, R. (2022). The price of actor diversity: Measuring project developers’ willingness to accept risks in renewable energy auctions. *Energy Policy*, 163, 112835. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.112835>
- Côté, E., & Salm, S. (2022). Risk-adjusted preferences of utility companies and institutional investors for battery storage and green hydrogen investment. *Energy Policy*, 163, 112821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.112821>
- Cousse, J., Wüstenhagen, R., & Schneider, N. (2020). Mixed feelings on wind energy: Affective imagery and local concern driving social acceptance in Switzerland. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 70, 101676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101676>
- Dykes, K., Kitzing, L., Andersson, M., Pons-Seres de Brauwer, C., & Canét, H. (2020). Beyond LCOE: New assessment criteria for evaluating Wind Energy R&I. In *SETWind workshop*. <https://setwind.eu/beyond-lcoe-new-assessment-criteria-for-evaluating-wind-energy-ri/>
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- Määttä, S. (2021a). *Perspectives on Public Participation in the Low-Carbon Transition in Ireland*, NESC, Dublin.
<https://www.nesc.ie/publications/perspectives-on-micro-generation-public-participation-in-the-low-carbon-transition-in-ireland-mistral/>
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- Miller, A. (2020). *Energy Transition Pathways and the COVID-19 Pandemic: An analysis of the 'green recovery' responses in Denmark and Ireland* NESC, Dublin
<https://www.nesc.ie/publications/energy-transition-pathways-and-the-covid-19-pandemic-an-analysis-of-the-green-recovery-responses-in-denmark-and-ireland/> (accessed 06.04.2022)
- Reckermann, M., Omstedt, A., Soomere, T., Aigars, J., Akhtar, N., Bełdowska, M., ... & Zorita, E. (2022). Human impacts and their interactions in the Baltic Sea region. *Earth System Dynamics*, 13(1), 1-80.
<https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-13-1-2022>
- Sillak, S., Borch, K., & Sperling, K. (2021). Assessing co-creation in strategic planning for urban energy transitions. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 74, 101952.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.101952>
- Vespa, M., Kortsch, T., Hildebrand, J., Schweizer-Ries, P., & Volkmer, S. A. (2022). Not All Places Are Equal: Using Instagram to Understand Cognitions and Affect towards Renewable Energy Infrastructures. *Sustainability*, 14(7), 4071.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su14074071>
- Vuichard, P., Broughel, A., Wüstenhagen, R., Tabi, A., & Knauf, J. (2022). Keep it local and bird-friendly: Exploring the social acceptance of wind energy in Switzerland, Estonia, and Ukraine. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 88, 102508.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102508>
- Von, W., Loorbach, T., Wagner, D., Koretskaya, A., Wade, O., Krupnik, R., ... & Telesiene, B. (2020). Social Sciences and Humanities priority 100 research questions for renewable energy in Horizon Europe. (https://energy-shifts.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/D2.3_WG1_renewables.pdf)